

DIFFERENTIAL MAGNETISED REVERBERANCE NOSOLOGIES OF
PSORIATIC POLYARTHROPATHY WITH GOUTY POLYARTHROPATHY AND
ARTHRITIC POLYARTHRITIS

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The purpose of the study – amelioration of dispersal nosologies of psoriatic arthropathy. 120 patients with psoriatic, gouty polyarthropathies and arthritic arthritis superannuated from 18 to 58 second childhood were examined. each patients underwent photography of the pretentious intersections and magnetised reverberance imagery (MRI). Radiography, as a rule, revealed substitutions impressive the off-white configurations of the joints. During MRI in patients with psoriatic polyarthropathy, articular syndrome, the syndrome of extra-articular demonstrations of the instigative cognitive semantics was mean business subchondral wear and tear were perceived earlier than during radiography. In patients with urarthritis and arthritic arthritis, MRI furthermore mean business the syndrome of off-white inwardness edema. With gout, the syndrome of the materialization of tofuses was revealed. The psychoanalysis of the obtained consequences showed that the application of magnetised reverberance imagery make-believe it accomplishable to aggrandizement the enlightenment cognitive operation of clinical and dispersal interrogation of patients with psoriatic polyarthropathy.

Introduction

The prevalence of psoriasis in the population is 1-3%. About 2.8 million patients with psoriasis have been registered in Russia. Signs of arthritis are detected in 13.5-47.0% of patients in this category [4, 6, 10]. In modern conditions, psoriatic arthropathy (PA) more often begins with damage to the joints of the hands (47.0%). In 43-74% of patients with psoriasis, skin lesions precede arthritis, but in 15% of cases, joint syndrome is detected before psoriatic rashes [4, 5]. In recent years, there has been a tendency to rejuvenation of this disease, its rapid progression and early disability of patients [9-11]. In the early stages of development, psoriatic polyarthropathy may occur under the guise of other inflammatory polyarthropathies, such as, for example, gouty polyarthropathy or rheumatoid arthritis [3]. A common problem in the diagnosis of these diseases remains the early detection of changes in the joints and their differential diagnosis, since only timely and properly prescribed specific treatment ensures the continued functioning of the articular apparatus and the improvement of the patient's quality of life. The main method of radiation diagnosis of psoriatic polyarthropathy is still standard or microfocus radiography [2, 7, 8, 12]. In some cases, in the presence of the disease, changes in the joints are not detected on radiographs

or they are minimal and nonspecific for this pathology [7, 8, 12]. Therefore, standard and microfocus radiography in the diagnosis of the early stage of this disease are ineffective. Due to the good resolution in relation to soft tissues, both extra- and intraarticular, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) can be considered as an effective method in the diagnosis of changes in the joints in psoriasis [1, 12]. The aim of our study was to improve the radiation diagnosis of psoriatic polyarthropathy.

Material and methods

Clinical, region and dispersal investigations of 120 patients superannuated 18 to 58 second childhood with instigative polyarthropathies were carried out. Of these, thither were 70 (58. 3%) women and 50 (41. 7%) men. The apportionment of patients by nosological configurations is shown in the table. each patients underwent photography of the pretentious intersections in cardinal touchstone protuberances on the Serigraf CF (Siemens) gimmick and MRI on Magnetom perceive (Siemens) and Magnetom Espree (Siemens) contrivances with a magnetised environment capability of 1. 5 T. MRI of the intersections was performed in axial, sagittal and adornment projections. A bendable curlicue was euphemistic pre-owned to contemplate joints, a quadrature imagination coil; in the contemplate of knowledgeable intersections and ileosacral intersections - a curlicue for the integral dead end in the contemplate of spinal intersections - a spinal coil. interrogation of comprehensive intersections was carried elsewhere with a tomographic transaction of 3 mm, inconsequential intersections - with a transaction of 2 mm. The touchstone standards of behaviour included throbbing progressions that allowed to accomplish T1-weighted representations (T1-VI), T2-weighted representations (T2-VI) and T1-VI and T2-VI with discontinuation of the expression from fat.

Results and discussion

Touchstone photography revealed no diseased substitutions in the intersections in 9 (7. 5%) of the examined patients. In 93 (77. 5%) patients, to a certain well-defined periarticular osteoporosis was detected. constricting of ultraviolet rays articulary apertures was perceived in 94 (78. 3%) cases. Subchondral osteosclerosis was perceived in 31 (25. 8%) patients. insignificant off-white developments on articulary integuments were envisioned in 32 (26. 7%) people. In 18 (15. 0%) patients, unmarry subchondral wear and tear were detected, which were bounteous recurrently decentralized in the proximal interphalangeal (n=15), metacarpophalangeal (n=10) joints. Subchondral wear and tear were dimly visible. In 33 (27. 5%) cases, cysts with clear, all the more contours, with a periphery of osteosclerosis in the environment of off-white epiphyses (topuses) were detected. In 84 (70. 0%) patients, the publication of periarticular compressible interweaves in the pretentious intersections was unsymmetrically increased. In patients with psoriatic polyarthropathy , MRI mean business articulary syndrome, the syndrome of extra-articular demonstrations of the instigative cognitive semantics and the syndrome of materialization of subchondral erosions. In psoriatic polyarthropathy, asymmetrical lesions of the lateral interphalangeal intersections of the participation (75. 0%) and lateral and proximal interphalangeal intersections of the feet (20. 0%) were bounteous recurrently observed. articulary syndrome during MRI manifested itself in the configuration of substitutions in cartilage,

synovial membrane, the formal propinquity of outburst in the reefer cavity, bursitis. odd dilution or devastation (n=10) of articulary gristle in the interphalangeal, metacarpophalangeal and carpus intersections was perceived in 16 patients. The MR expression from it was homogenous in 30. 0% of patients. odd dilution of articulary gristle was envisioned in 16 cases. In 16 patients, the synovium of the intersections was unequally thickened, its contours were clear, uneven. A homogenous outburst was perceived in the reefer opening in 16 cases. The syndrome of extra-articular demonstrations of the instigative cognitive semantics was celebrated in the configuration of tendosynovitis and asymmetrical hydrops of periarticular compressible tissues. tendosynovitis was characterized in 11 general public as an odd condensing of the synovial muscularity sheaths with the formal propinquity of outburst in them. The characteristic synovial vagina of the flexor muscles of the hand, the synovial vaginas of the flexors of the digits of the hand, the synovial vagina of the extensor of the inconsiderable fingerbreadth of the hand, the synovial vaginas of the far-reaching flexor of the pollex and flexors of the toes were bounteous recurrently affected. asymmetrical hydrops of periarticular compressible interweaves without contravention of their specialization was perceived in 14 cases. Subchondral wear and tear of the articulary integuments of castanets were envisioned in 10 patients as a flat, allantoid or cuneate insufficiency of the cortical off-white with clear, odd contours ranging in proportion from 1. 0 to 3. 0 mm. Hypointensive periphery of osteosclerosis was perceived on the circumference of subchondral wear and tear in 90. 0% of cases. Subchondral wear and tear in psoriasis were bounteous recurrently envisioned in the environment of the articulary integuments of the phalanges of the guardianships and feet, metacarpal bones, castanets of the proximal string of the carpus and at the situation of adherence of the articulary capsule. substitutions in the intersections in arthritic arthritis and gouty polyarthropathy, discriminating of the articulary syndrome, differed relatively from consubstantial demonstrations in psoriatic arthritis. In 91 (91. 0%) patients, odd dilution or devastation (n=75) of articulary gristle was visualized. annihilative substitutions in reefer gristle in rheumatism and gouty arthropathy were perceived earlier from the onslaught of the affliction and were bounteous well-defined compared to psoriatic arthropathy. In 87 (87. 0%) cases, the synovial membrane of the intersections was unequally thickened. In gouty, as in psoriatic, arthropathy, the contours of the synovium were clear, uneven. Patients with rheumatism had a bounteous well-defined escalation of the synovial membrane of the joints. Pannus was perceived in 16. 0% of patients with rheumatism in the configuration of anesthetic hyperplasia of synovial interweave conterminous to the articulary aboveground of the bone. Subchondral flatbed wear and tear with indistinct, odd contours were perceived in the environment of the pannus conterminous to the off-white in each patients of this group. Pannus was isointensive on T1-VI and T2-VI. In 84 (84. 0%) patients, outburst was envisioned in the reefer cavity. contrastive with psoriatic arthropathy, in urarthrits – in 20. 0% of cases, and in patients with arthritic arthritis in 24. 0% of cases, the outburst was heterogeneous. In 29 (29. 0%) patients with stifle and cubitus reefer lesions, indications of bursitis were perceived in the configuration of odd condensing of the articulary shopping bag of the reefer and the formal propinquity of outburst in it. In differentiate to patients with

psoriatic polyarthropathy, 23 (23. 0%) patients with urarthritis (n=10) and rheumatism (n=13) had marrow hydrops syndrome. With the syndrome of marrow hydrops in the epiphyses or subchondral percentages of the bones, hyperintensive – on T2-weighted and hypointensive – on T1-weighted tomograms spaces with fuzzy, odd contours were determined. In the syndrome of extra-articular demonstrations of the instigative cognitive semantics tendosynovitis was perceived in 52 (52. 0%) general public and asymmetrical hydrops of periarticular compressible interweaves was envisioned in 71 (71. 0%) cases. In arthritic arthritis, the corresponding synovial muscularity sheaths were bounteous recurrently pretentious as in psoriatic polyarthropathy. In gouty arthropathy, the synovial vagina of the hallux was bounteous affected. In arthritic arthritis, contrastive with gouty and psoriatic polyarthropathies, moreover to asymmetrical edema, thither was a contravention of specialization of periarticular compressible tissues. In arthritic arthritis, as in psoriatic polyarthropathy, the syndrome of materialization of subchondral wear and tear was revealed. Subchondral wear and tear in arthritic arthritis (n=42) were without the periphery of osteosclerosis, decentralized bounteous recurrently in the castanets of the wrist, metacarpal castanets and articular integuments of the proximal phalanges of the II–III digits of the hand. Subchondral cysts were perceived in 21 (42. 0%) patients with arthritic arthritis in the configuration of a allantoid insufficiency of the subchondral off-white with clear, all the more or odd contours, ranging in proportion from 1 to 3 mm. The cysts had a hyperintensive MR expression on T2-VI and a hypointensive MR expression on T1-VI and in virtually containers were with a hypointensive periphery of osteosclerosis on the periphery. In patients with gout, MRI mean business the syndrome of materialization of gouty nodes (tofuses).

In 42 (84. 0%) cases, in the epiphyses, off-white metaphyses or periarticular compressible tissues, subcortically situated allantoid materializations ranging from 3 mm in thickness to 6 × 4 mm in size, with clear, odd contours, and in 26. 0% of cases, with a hypointensive periphery of osteosclerosis on the circumference (tofuses) were mean business to be enthusiastically hyperintensive on T2-VI and hypointensive on T1-VI. Intra-articular localisation of tofuses was ascertained in 15 (35. 7%) general public intra- and extra-articular localisation – in 21 (50. 0%) patients. With intra-articular localisation of tofuses, the borders of the articular integuments of castanets were bounteous recurrently damaged. Extra-articular topuses were decentralized partially in the cortical stratum of the metaepiphyses and diaphyses of bones, partially in the conterminous compressible tissues. In 35 (83. 3%) patients, tofuses were envisioned in the periarticular compressible interweaves or compressible interweaves of the joint. bounteous recurrently they were decentralized underneath the ligaments and tendons of the muscles. MRI was the disposition of selection in the designation and calculation designation of articular syndrome and marrow hydrops syndrome. The effectualness of MRI was higher-calibre thereto of touchstone photography in sleuthing subchondral wear and tear and tofuses. When imagery subchondral wear and tear the specificity of photography was 1. 7% higher than the specificity of MRI. patch the over-sensitivity and faithfulness of MRI exceeded these pointers in photography by 31. 4 and 9. 8%, respectively. The prognosticality of a

cocksureness determination of these undergrounds was 96. 3% - with MRI and 94. 7% - with radiography, the prognosticality of a contradiction determination was 75. 3 and 69. 6%, respectively. When imagery tofuses, the over-sensitivity of MRI was 93. 5%, specificity was 80. 0%, faithfulness was 94. 3%, whereas with photography these pointers reached 82. 7, 66. 7 and 80. 0%, respectively. The prognosticality of a cocksureness determination of these undergrounds was 96. 6% - with MRI, 91. 7% - with radiography, the prognosticality of a contradiction determination was 66. 7 and 44. 4%, respectively.

Заклучение.

The application of MRI make-believe it accomplishable to importantly aggrandizement the communicative expenditure of clinical and dispersal interrogation of patients with psoriatic polyarthropathy. It make-believe it accomplishable to imagine substitutions in the intersections discriminating of articular syndrome (changes in articular cartilage, synovium, articular bags), which are not mean business by radiography. Also, with MRI, the localization, size, and constitution of subchondral wear and tear could be assessed with in a superior way efficiency. moreover, MRI allowed calculation designation of psoriatic polyarthropathy with gouty polyarthropathy and arthritic arthritis.

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